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What kind of leaders can promote the disclosure of information on the sustainable development goals?

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Abstract

As the person responsible for a company's strategies and disclosure policies, the CEO is the architect of its CSR strategy. This paper analyzes which CEO's attributes influence the level of disclosure of information about business contribution to the SDGs. Based on the Upper Echelons Theory, a set of hypotheses on the influence of several CEO attributes (demographic and professional characteristics as well as personal traits) on SDGs disclosure have been tested in a sample of the leading Spanish companies for the period 2015–2021 using ordinal regressions for panel data. The results show that education level, nationality, and narcissism are the CEO attributes that significantly affect the level of SDG disclosure. Specifically, companies whose CEOs have a higher level of education, are Spanish (local), and are narcissist tend to disclose more information about the SDGs. This study aims to contribute to literature by providing new empirical evidence on an emerging research topic and by providing a glimpse into the CEO “profile” that may favor a company's propensity to disclose information on the SDGs.

KEYWORDS

2030 agenda, chief executive officer, SDG reporting, sustainable development goals, upper echelons theory

1 | INTRODUCTION

The 2030 Agenda and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) have brought about a shift in corporate social responsibility (CSR) strategies, characterized by a proactive approach that allows companies to identify “sustainable development trajectories” (ElAlfy et al., 2020), based on the SDGs most pertinent to their field of business (Jun & Kim, 2021). As García-Sánchez, Amor-Esteban, and Galindo-Álvarez (2020) point out, the 2030 Agenda embodies a “point of convergence” for CSR strategies, so that the degree of alignment of business strategies with the SDGs can be considered an indicator of the firm's sustainability success (van Zanten & van Tulder, 2021).

Commitment to the SDGs can provide companies with tangible and intangible benefits, which requires companies to communicate

relevant information about their contribution to the SDGs (García-Sánchez, Amor-Esteban, & Galindo-Álvarez, 2020). However, the decision to integrate the SDGs into business strategy and disclose information on the SDGs is “a voluntary choice”, conditioned by both institutional and internal factors that transcend business incentives (García-Sánchez, Aibar-Guzmán, Aibar-Guzmán, & Somohano-Rodríguez, 2022, p. 514). In particular, key organizational actors may play a significant role in promoting business commitment to the 2030 Agenda and SDG reporting. In this sense, according to a global survey conducted by Accenture and UN Global Compact on CEO attitudes towards the SDGs, CEOs think that the SDGs represent an opportunity to reconsider corporate approaches to sustainable value creation and consider that the SDGs provide a good framework for structuring their firms' sustainability efforts (Accenture & UN Global Compact, 2019) in order to generate

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the desired impacts on stakeholders, the environment, and society (Shayan et al., 2022).

Given that CSR-related decisions are subject to managerial discretion (García-Sánchez & Martínez-Ferrero, 2019; Hambrick & Finkelstein, 1987), they will be strongly affected by the CEO's interests and preferences (Arena et al., 2018). In this regard, CEOs' demographic characteristics, values, and cognitive styles, by affecting how they perceive the environment, will influence their companies' CSR strategies and performance (Aibar-Guzmán & Frías-Aceituno, 2021; Lewis et al., 2014; Petrenko et al., 2016), which allows to explain the diversity in CSR practices. This can be explained on the basis of the Upper Echelons Theory (UET) (Hambrick & Mason, 1984), according to which differences in the idiosyncratic characteristics and cognitive styles of top executives influence their decisions, thus affecting corporate strategic choices they make (White & Borgholthaus, 2022). This theoretical framework has become "one of the most influential perspectives" guiding research on how managers' characteristics and experiences impact on firm outcomes (Bromiley & Rau, 2016; Neely et al., 2020). Thus, over the last decade, a growing stream of research has drawn on the UET to analyze how CEO observable and unobservable characteristics affect CSR practices (Aibar-Guzmán & Frías-Aceituno, 2021; Bertrand et al., 2021; García-Sánchez, Aibar-Guzmán, et al., 2020; Hewa Heenipellage et al., 2022; Lewis et al., 2014; Liao et al., 2019). This research stream has provided empirical evidence regarding the CEO attributes that may favor CSR engagement and reporting.

As regards the 2030 Agenda, in their case study of an Australian aquaculture company, Fleming et al. (2017) found that the CEO's personal values positively affect SDG engagement; and van Zanten and van Tulder (2018) observed that the fact that the CEO of the multinational firm they studied was a leading member of the UN SDG advisory group influenced the firm's strategy in relation to the SDGs. However, to the best of our knowledge, no previous study has analyzed the effect of CEO's attributes on business commitment to the 2030 Agenda and SDG reporting. In view that the 2030 Agenda and the SDGs suppose a "paradigm shift" for academic research on CSR, it would be worth asking what kind of business leaders can promote corporate commitment to and disclosure of information on the SDGs.

Considering that "where there is limited concern, there will be limited disclosure" (Deegan, 2002, p. 335), the study of the drivers of SDG reporting may help to promote effective business commitment to the 2030 Agenda as well as provide valuable information regarding the actions performed by firms to achieve the SDGs. In this sense, several authors have highlighted the need of understand what factors drive SDG reporting (Izzo et al., 2020; Tsalis et al., 2020). However, most studies have focused on institutional-level factors, firm-level factors, and governance-level factors that may affect a firm's propensity to disclose SDG information. Indeed, apart from García-Sánchez, Aibar-Guzmán, Aibar-Guzmán, and Somohano-Rodríguez (2022), who analyzed the effect of two CEO personal attributes (gender and educational background), no previous study has analyzed the influence of CEO demographic characteristics, values, and cognitive styles on SDG reporting. As Al-Shammari et al. (2019, p. 113) stress, while external

factors are relevant, focusing exclusively on them gives, at best, an incomplete picture of the drivers of a company's CSR activities. This paper aims to fill this gap in literature by analyzing how CEO's personal attributes influence the level of disclosure on SDG-related initiatives. Given that SDG reporting can be considered "an extension to, or evolution of, corporate responsibility reporting" (Izzo et al., 2020, p. 11), considering the broad scope of the SDGs, we want to know whether the characteristics of the CEO that affect CSR disclosure would also apply to SDG disclosure.

For this purpose, we focus on the Spanish context. Based on a sample of the leading Spanish companies for the period 2015–2021, the results show that education level, nationality, and narcissism are the CEO attributes that significantly affect SDG disclosure. Specifically, those companies whose CEOs have a higher level of education, are Spanish (local), and are narcissist disclose more information on the SDGs. In addition, considering that some CEO attributes can moderate (reinforce or inhibit) the effect of the remaining ones on SDG disclosure, we analyze the jointly effect of CEO attributes on SDG reporting. We found that some combinations of CEO attributes have a significant effect on SDG reporting. Specifically, this is the case of age and tenure (companies with older CEOs who have been in the company shorter disclose more information on the SDGs), age and narcissism (companies with older and narcissist CEOs disclose more information on the SDGs), education and tenure (companies with CEOs with a high level of education and who have also been in the company shorter disclose less information on the SDGs), and tenure and narcissism (companies with narcissist CEOs who have also been in the company longer disclose more information on the SDGs).

This study contributes to literature extending the empirical evidence on the determinants of SDG reporting. We suggest that greater emphasis should be placed on the attributes of the key decision maker in the company and analyze their individual and joint effect by showing that some CEO attributes, when combined with others, may produce stronger or contradictory effects on SDG reporting. Thus, our study differs from prior research in that is one of the few studies that (1) considers both observable (education, nationality, and tenure) and unobservable (narcissism) characteristics of CEOs (Hewa Heenipellage et al., 2022), (2) analyzes both the individual and joint effect of these characteristics (Chu et al., 2022; Villalba-Ríos et al., 2022), and (3) addresses the study of the effect of CEO observable and unobservable characteristics in the context of the 2030 Agenda. This broad scope allows us to envision the CEO "profile" that may favor a firm's propensity to disclose SDG information.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: after this introduction, the next section presents the theoretical framework and the development of the research hypotheses. Section 3 describes the empirical study's designs (sample, method, model, and variables). In Section 4, the main results are presented and discussed. Section 5 presents the results of a complementary analysis. Section 6 discusses the theoretical and practical implications of the findings and, finally, Section 7 summarizes the main conclusions of the study, outlines its limitations, and suggests future research avenues.

2 | THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

From a theoretical perspective, the UET postulates that managers' demographic characteristics and experiences mold their values and management styles, which in turn influences their decisions and performance (Hambrick & Mason, 1984). This theoretical framework proposes that there are “linkages among individuals, organizations, and their competitive environments” (Hambrick & Mason, 1984, p. 193), so that managers make decisions based on how they interpret the context surrounding the decision, and these interpretations are partial and are biased by their individual characteristics and experiences (Wang et al., 2015). Hence, managers will make different decisions based on their personal characteristics, values, and cognitive styles (Bamber et al., 2010; Liao et al., 2019).

As the main responsible for a company's strategies and disclosure policies (Aguinis & Glavas, 2012; Li et al., 2018), the CEO is also the architect of its CSR strategy (García-Sánchez & Martínez-Ferrero, 2019). Given that CEOs perceive the environment and, consequently value CSR differently (Cordeiro & Sarkis, 2008) depending on their characteristics, cognitive styles, backgrounds, and experiences (Aibar-Guzmán & Frías-Aceituno, 2021; García-Sánchez, Aibar-Guzmán, et al., 2020), CSR-related decisions will be biased by the CEO's attributes (Villalba-Ríos et al., 2022). Thus, prior research has documented the influence of several observable and unobservable CEO attributes on CSR strategies and disclosure policies (e.g., Chu et al., 2022; García-Sánchez, Aibar-Guzmán, et al., 2020; Hewa Heenipellage et al., 2022; Lewis et al., 2014; Li et al., 2018; Liao et al., 2019; Manner, 2010; Oh et al., 2016; Petrenko et al., 2016; Tang et al., 2018).

According to Hewa Heenipellage et al. (2022), studies based on the UET have followed three different approaches: (1) considering only observable characteristics (e.g., age, tenure or education), (2) considering only unobservable traits (e.g., charisma, hubris, narcissism, overconfidence or ability), and (3) considering both observable and unobservable characteristics. They noted that most studies fall into the first two approaches, providing an incomplete picture of how CEO characteristics affect business decisions, and called for studies that combine both observable and unobservable CEO characteristics. In response to this call, in this study we consider three observable demographic and professional characteristics (education, nationality, and tenure) and one unobservable personal trait (narcissism) of CEOs that prior research has found significantly affect CSR reporting. This choice is justified because we consider these attributes to be paramount in explaining a CEO's “personal construal” of strategic choices (Hambrick, 2007, p. 334) and predicting its effect on firm performance from the perspective of the UET (Hambrick & Mason, 1984); they are among the CEO attributes most analyzed in literature (Bromiley & Rau, 2016; Neely et al., 2020; White & Borgholthaus, 2022); and the analysis of their impact on CSR has yielded mixed results, suggesting the need for further study (Villalba-Ríos et al., 2022). Thus, they will allow us to determine the CEO profile that can promote effective sustainability reporting in the context of the 2030 Agenda.

2.1 | Education

Among the CEO's demographic characteristics, education has been found to be important determinant of CSR strategies (Borghesi et al., 2014; Huang, 2013; Lewis et al., 2014; Tang et al., 2015; Velte, 2019; Yuan et al., 2017). Education shapes the moral and ethical values individuals (Frank et al., 1993; Hambrick & Mason, 1984; Manner, 2010) and favors open-mindedness (Wei et al., 2018). Prior studies have shown that individuals' education level, defined as “the formal qualification in the form of degrees individuals receive from college or university” (Shahzadi et al., 2019, p. 1242), influences their thought processes increasing sensitivity towards social and environmental issues (Garrido-Ruso & Aibar-Guzmán, 2022; Hewa Heenipellage et al., 2022; Sun et al., 2020). From this perspective, the higher the CEO's level of education, the more concerned he/she is about sustainability challenges and the more aware he/she is of the importance of disclosing information about the social and environmental activities of his/her company (Malik et al., 2020).

On the other hand, an individual's educational background (i.e., the type of studies that she/he has attended) also affects her/his cognitive models of decision-making (Hambrick & Mason, 1984). Thus, some authors argue that economics studies negatively affect the individual's concern for ethical and social issues (Frank et al., 1993) while training in the humanities has the opposite effect (Davis et al., 2018). To the extent that the curriculum design of most business schools includes ethics (Huang, 2013), CEOs with MBAs would tend to adopt a proactive approach regarding CSR, promoting their firms CSR-related initiatives (Finkelstein et al., 2009; Huang, 2013; Lewis et al., 2014). Likewise, CSR training can favor CEO's awareness of, and engagement with, the SDGs (García-Sánchez, Aibar-Guzmán, Aibar-Guzmán, & Somohano-Rodríguez, 2022). In a recent study, Villalba-Ríos et al. (2022) found that CEOs that have studied an engineering degree and an MBA configure firms with high CSR performance.

Several studies document a positive relationship between CEO education level and CSR performance and reporting (Huang, 2013; Lewis et al., 2014; Ma et al., 2019), suggesting that education makes CEOs more and related disclosure needs (Malik et al., 2020). We take the view that the CEO's education level influence he/she decisions regarding disclosure policies and, based on the above discussion, it can be expected that firms with CEOs with a higher education level are more likely to develop an adequate SDG reporting strategy. Accordingly, the following hypothesis is stated:

H₁: Companies with CEOs with a high level of education will report more SDG information.

2.2 | Nationality

As a consequence of the globalization of the economy and the internationalization of companies, the presence of foreigners in top management is becoming more and more frequent (Al-Duais et al., 2021).

The national origin of executives influences their mindsets and how they interpret and respond to strategic issues (Nielsen & Nielsen, 2013). However, few studies have analyzed the effect that the nationality of the CEO has on decisions related to CSR.

Hometown identity is “a psychological bias” whereby individuals are inclined to make decisions that favor their hometowns because of affective-emotional bonds (Ren et al., 2021, p. 758). Beyond emotional ties, there is a cognitive mechanism by which a personal identity is established in relation to the place where an individual was born and grew up (Hernández et al., 2010). This place identity affects the behavior of individuals, making them more inclined to become involved in protecting their hometown environment and the welfare of their hometown community (Carrus et al., 2005). Thus, some authors have analyzed the effect of hometown identity on managers' decision-making, showing that they tend to make decisions that are beneficial to their hometowns (Jiang et al., 2019; Yonker, 2017).

According to Al-Duais et al. (2021) CEOs may feel morally compelled to contribute to mitigating or solving the social and environmental problems of their hometown, so that local CEOs would encourage social and environmental initiatives. In this regard, Ren et al. (2021) showed a positive association between the company's headquarters being located in the CEO's hometown and eco-innovation. Nevertheless, Bertrand et al. (2021) argue the opposite argument by considering that foreign CEOs tend to promote CSR initiatives in order to enhance their legitimacy among local stakeholders. They showed that firms with foreign CEOs have a higher corporate social performance than those firms with local CEOs.

Despite the limited and contradictory empirical evidence, we expect that working in a company located in their own country will make local CEOs feel more committed to making decisions that may affect the company's environment and, consequently, promote commitment to the 2030 Agenda in their companies. Therefore, we propose the following hypothesis:

H₂: Companies with local CEOs will report more SDG information.

2.3 | Tenure

Literature considers tenure as one of the most influential characteristics that affect CEO decision-making (Velte, 2019). According to Hambrick and Mason (1984, p. 200), “career experiences partially shape the lenses through which they view current strategic opportunities and problems”, so that CEOs modify their patterns of behavior over the years their tenure. There are two alternative views regarding the effect of CEO tenure on CSR (Oh et al., 2018; Villalba-Ríos et al., 2022). On the one hand, the “human capital view” posits that longer tenured CEOs have more experience and knowledge about the company (Al-Duais et al., 2021; Oh et al., 2018), which allows them to “see the business case for many types of CSR initiatives” (Manner, 2010, p. 57). Furthermore, tenure makes individuals to feel more connected with their firms and

tend to associate their own reputation to that of their firms (Garrido-Ruso & Aibar-Guzmán, 2022). Consequently, longer-tenured CEOs are more likely to engage in CSR activities and, therefore, there would be a positive association between CEO tenure and CSR reporting.

On the other hand, several authors propose an inverse relationship between CEO tenure and CSR, supporting this view with several arguments. Firstly, the “career concern hypothesis” (Chen et al., 2019; Khan et al., 2021) suggests that CEOs in the early stages of their tenure need to signal their ability and build confidence among directors, shareholders, and stakeholders. Accordingly, early-tenured CEOs may look for enhancing their reputation through initiatives related to CSR and signaling their abilities through CSR reporting. Secondly, the “career horizon hypothesis” (Chen et al., 2019; Khan et al., 2021) suggests that the longer the career horizon, the more incentive CEOs have to support projects with long-term results, while a short career horizon encourages short-termism. Therefore, since it is assumed that early-tenured CEOs have a longer career horizon, they will tend to support CSR-related initiatives, including reporting, as they believe they can benefit from their results. Thirdly, the “fixed paradigm view” (McClelland et al., 2012; Oh et al., 2018) poses that long tenure reduces the CEOs' cognitive flexibility and favors resistance to change (Hambrick & Fukutoni, 1991), making CEOs reluctant to respond to new stakeholders' demands (Miller, 1991). Additionally, long tenure is typically associated with more CEO power and security (Malik et al., 2020), so that they are able to handle stakeholder pressures (Khan et al., 2021). All these effects collectively support a negative association between CEO tenure and CSR performance and disclosure.

Prior studies provide mixed findings. Although most studies document a positive relationship between CEO tenure and CSR (Thomas & Simerly, 1994; Huang, 2013; Wei et al., 2018; Cho et al., 2019; Malik et al., 2020; Vilallolba-Ríos et al., 2022), others find a negative (Chen et al., 2019; Chen et al., 2021; Khan et al., 2021) or no significant relationship (Al-Shammari et al., 2019). Considering the above arguments, we take the view that tenure will negatively affect SDG reporting, and, hence, the following hypothesis is stated:

H₃: Companies with early-tenured CEOs will report more SDG information.

2.4 | Narcissism

Narcissists are individuals who partially interpret reality “because it is reflected in their own image and constantly seek attention and reinforcement of their positive self-views” (Petrenko et al., 2016, p. 265). Narcissistic individuals have an attention-seeking behavior looking for fame, admiration, and popularity (Bodolica & Spraggon, 2011; Chatterjee & Hambrick, 2007). These individuals show a high degree of self-love and self-admiration (Al-Shammari et al., 2019; Tang et al., 2018).

According to Kim et al. (2018), CSR is a perfect tool for CEOs to be in the spotlight and, used well, it provides them with a positive image and reputation. Moreover, narcissistic CEOs will try to avoid criticism stemming from socially irresponsible actions (Petrenko et al., 2016). Consequently, narcissistic CEOs tend to invest more in CSR initiatives than less narcissistic CEOs (Petrenko et al., 2016; Al-Shanmari et al., 2019). Given that activities related to the 2030 Agenda are increasingly present in the media and that these decisions are often linked to CEOs, these well-executed initiatives will result in a positive image of the CEO (Lin et al., 2022; Tang et al., 2018).

Therefore, business commitment to the 2030 Agenda can be seen by narcissistic CEOs as a means to attract positive attention from the media and stakeholders, thus satisfying their psychological needs of admiration and praise (Al-Shanmari et al., 2019). Accordingly, we consider that narcissistic CEOs will view SDG reporting as a way to increase the attention directed towards them and, therefore, we propose the following hypothesis:

H₄: Companies with narcissistic CEOs will report more SDG information.

3 | METHODOLOGY

3.1 | Sample

As indicated earlier, this study is focused on the Spanish context. We focus on Spain because is a country with a high commitment to the SDGs and is one of the leading countries in the European Union in terms of non-financial reporting (Boto-Álvarez & García-Fernández, 2020; Curtó-Pagès et al., 2021). Following García-Sánchez et al. (2022b), the sample selected to carry out the study is made up of the 35 companies belonging to the IBEX-35 index, which includes the most liquid stocks traded on the Spanish stock market, composed of the largest Spanish listed firms (Hernández-Madrigal et al., 2020). This choice is justified because they are the leading Spanish companies in terms of CSR reporting (Pérez-Calderon et al., 2021; García-Sánchez, Aibar-Guzmán, Serrano-Valdecillos, & Aibar-Guzmán, 2022). Table 1 provides information regarding the companies that make up the sample.

The information was obtained from the companies' corporate reports and web pages as well as from the Iberian Balance Analysis System (SABI) database. The period of study covers from 2015 (the year in which the 2030 Agenda was established) to 2021 (the latest year with available data). Thus, we obtained an unbalanced data panel consisting of 245 observations.

3.2 | Empirical model

In order to test the research hypotheses, we propose the model represented by Equation (1).

TABLE 1 Sample information

Companies	Activity sector
Acciona	Basic Materials, Industry and Construction
Acerinox	Basic Materials, Industry and Construction
ACS	Basic Materials, Industry and Construction
Aena	Consumer Services
Almirall	Consumer Good
Amadeus	Technology and Telecommunications
ArcelorMittal	Basic Mat., Industry and Construction
Banco Sabadell	Financial Services
Banco Santander	Financial Services
Bankinter	Financial Services
BBVA	Financial Services
CaixaBank	Financial Services
Cellnex	Technology and Telecommunications
CIE Automotive	Basic Materials, Industry and Construction
Colonial	Real Estate Services
Enagás	Petrol and Power
Endesa	Petrol and Power
Ferrovial	Basic Materials, Industry and Construction
Fluidra	Basic Materials, Industry and Construction
Grifols	Consumer Goods
IAG	Consumer Services
Iberdrola	Petrol and Power
Indra	Technology and Telecommunications
Inditex	Consumer Goods
Mapfre	Financial Services
Meliá	Consumer Services
Merlin Properties	Real Estate Services
Naturgy	Petrol and Power
Pharmamar	Consumer Goods
Red Eléctrica	Petrol and Power
Repsol	Petrol and Power
Rovi	Consumer Goods
Siemens Gamesa	Basic Materials, Industry and Construction
Solaria	Petrol and Power
Telefónica	Technology and Telecommunications

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{SDG}_{i,t} = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{education}_{i,t} + \beta_2 \text{nationality}_{i,t} + \beta_3 \text{tenure}_{i,t} \\
 & + \beta_4 \text{narcissism}_{i,t} + \beta_5 \text{gender}_{i,t} + \beta_6 \text{age}_{i,t} + \beta_7 \text{bsize}_{i,t} \\
 & + \beta_8 \text{bindep}_{i,t} + \beta_9 \text{bdiversity}_{i,t} + \beta_{10} \text{CEOduality}_{i,t} \quad (1) \\
 & + \beta_{11} \text{CSRcom}_{i,t} + \beta_{12} \text{fsize}_{i,t} + \beta_{13} \text{fage}_{i,t} + \beta_{14} \text{ROA}_{i,t} \\
 & + \beta_{15} \text{COVID}_{i,t} + \beta_{16} \text{Industry}_t + \beta_{17} \text{Year}_t + \varepsilon_{i,t} + \eta_{i,t}
 \end{aligned}$$

Where *i* and *t* represent the company and the year, respectively; η represents the unobservable heterogeneity and ε is the linear estimation disturbance or residual. Additionally, we controlled for the sector (Industry) and period (Year).

Regarding the analysis technique, due to the censored nature of the dependent variable, which takes values in a concrete range, 0 or 1, the estimation is performed using Tobit regression for panel data with STATA 17.0 software, which has been used in previous work on the subject (e.g., García-Sánchez, Aibar-Guzmán, Serrano-Valdecillos, & Aibar-Guzmán, 2022). Indicate that the Tobit estimator considers that the SDG reporting variable is right- and left-censored and provides coefficient estimates that are efficient and consistent.

3.3 | Variables

3.3.1 | Dependent variable: SDG reporting

To determine the level of SDG disclosure by each of the companies, we followed the following steps. Following other studies on CSR disclosure (Hummel & Rötzel, 2019; Hummel & Skezely, 2022), we first conducted a textual analysis to check which reports included information on the SDGs. We established the following search pattern “SDGs”, “SDGs*”, “SDG*”, “Sustainable Development Goal”, “Sustainable Development Goal*”. Once we had identified the reports that provided the information we were looking for, we conducted a content analysis of them.

Each author separately analyzed each report and determined a value associated with the level of SDG disclosure using as a guide the instrument developed by Hummel and Szekely (2022), shown in Table 2. This measurement scheme was derived from the recommendations on SDG reporting set out by the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) and the United Nations Global Compact (2018). As can be seen in Table 2, Hummel and Szekely (2022) differentiate two aspects of SDG disclosure: the “definition and prioritization of the SDGs” (DEF) and the “measurement and analysis of the SDGs” (MEA). Thus, DEF would reflect the company’s business commitment and general philosophy regarding SDG reporting, while MEA focuses on specific attributes of disclosures (e.g., quantitative and qualitative information, forward-looking statements, etc.). Thus, we assigned a value of 1 when the answer to the item’s question was yes, and a value of 0 otherwise.

The results of the analysis were then compared and the differences were discussed and reconciled. Finally, the SDG variable was created as the sum of the responses to the questions, taking values between 0 and 11. This variable allows us to measure “the quality of explicit SDG disclosure in firms’ annual reports” (Hummel & Szekely, 2022, p. 161). A similar approach (i.e., computing a score from the sum of several items) has been previously used by other authors (e.g., García-Sánchez et al., 2023) and it does not make a significant difference in determining CSR compared to more complex procedures and calculations (Amor-Esteban et al., 2020).

3.3.2 | Independent variables: CEO characteristics

The independent variables considered in this study are the personal and professional characteristics of CEOs, which were measured based on previous literature (e.g., Huang, 2013; Lewis et al., 2014; Lin

TABLE 2 SDG disclosure measurement

Disclosure indicator	Measurement
Definition and prioritization	
DEF1: Does the statement from the senior decision-maker reference the SDGs?	0 (no) / 1 (yes)
DEF2: Does the report provide general information on the SDGs?	0 (no) / 1 (yes)
DEF3: Does the report provide information on the process of SDG prioritization?	0 (no) / 1 (yes)
DEF4: Does the report provide information on the outcome of SDG prioritization (i.e., the SDGs they relate to)?	0 (no) / 1 (yes)
DEF5: Does the SDG prioritization relate to negative impacts in addition to positive ones?	0 (no) / 1 (yes)
Measurement and analysis	
MEA1: Does the report provide information on qualitative targets related to the SDGs?	0 (no) / 1 (yes)
MEA2: Does the report provide information on quantitative targets related to the SDGs?	0 (no) / 1 (yes)
MEA3: Does the report provide information on specific (past or ongoing) actions related to achieving the SDGs?	0 (no) / 1 (yes)
MEA4: Does the report provide qualitative information on the outcome of these actions?	0 (no) / 1 (yes)
MEA5: Does the report provide quantitative information on the outcome of these actions?	0 (no) / 1 (yes)
MEA6: Does the report provide information on future actions related to achieving the SDGs?	0 (no) / 1 (yes)

Note: Hummel & Szekely (2022, p. 161).

et al., 2022; Manner, 2010). Data for all the independent variables were obtained from the annual reports.

Thus, education level (education) was measured by establishing four categories: 1 = no university level degree, 2 = bachelor’s degree, 3 = Master’s degree and 4 = PhD degree. Nationality is a dummy variable, taking the value of 1 in the case of Spanish CEOs and 0 for foreign CEOs. Tenure reflects the number of years the CEO has been at the company as CEO.

To measure narcissism, we used the scale developed by Lin et al. (2022). Thus, based on the photos of the CEO published in the annual reports and different levels of narcissism were established: 1 = there is no photo of the CEO; 2 = there is a photo of the CEO in which she/he is accompanied by other people and it occupies less than half a page; 3 = there is a photo of the CEO in which she/he is accompanied by other people and it occupies more than half a page; 4 = there is a photo of the CEO alone and it occupies less than half a page; and 5 = there is a photo of the CEO alone and it occupies more than half a page.

3.3.3 | Control variables

In line with other studies (e.g., Al-Shammari et al., 2019; García-Sánchez, Aibar-Guzmán, Aibar-Guzmán, & Somohano-Rodríguez, 2022;

TABLE 3 Variable measurement

Variables	Acronym	Measurement	Data source	Authors	
Dependent variable	SDG Reporting	SDG	Scale from 0–11	Annual reports	Hummel and Szekely (2022)
Independent variables	CEO education level	education	1 = no university level degree 2 = bachelor degree 3 = Master's degree 4 = PhD degree	Annual reports	
	CEO nationality	nationality	1 = Spanish CEOs 0 = foreign CEOs	Annual reports	Huang (2013)
	CEO tenure	tenure	Number of years the CEO has been at the company as CEO	Annual reports	Manner (2010)
	CEO narcissism	narcissism	1 = there is no photo of the CEO 2 = there is a photo of the CEO accompanied by other people and it occupies less than half a page 3 = there is a photo of the CEO accompanied by other people and it occupies more than half a page 4 = there is a photo of the CEO alone and it occupies less than half a page 5 = there is a photo of the CEO alone and it occupies more than half a page.	Annual reports	Lin et al., (2022)
Control variables	CEO gender	gender	1 = woman 0 = man	Annual reports	García-Sánchez, Aibar-Guzmán, Aibar-Guzmán, and Somohano-Rodríguez (2022)
	CEO age	age	CEO's age	Annual reports	Manner (2010)
	Board size	bsize	Number of directors on the board	Annual reports	García-Sánchez, Aibar-Guzmán, Aibar-Guzmán, and Somohano-Rodríguez (2022)
	Board independence	bindep	Percentage of independent directors on the board	Annual reports	Al-Shammari et al. (2019)
	Board diversity	bdiversity	Percentage of female directors on the board	Annual reports	Al-Shammari et al. (2019)
	CEO duality	CEOduality	1 = if the CEO is also the chairperson of the board 0 = otherwise	Annual reports	Manner (2010)
	CSR commission	CSRcom	1 = there is a CSR commission 0 = otherwise	Annual reports	García-Sánchez, Aibar-Guzmán, Aibar-Guzmán, and Somohano-Rodríguez (2022)
	Firm size	fsize	logarithm of total assets	SABI	García-Sánchez, Aibar-Guzmán, Aibar-Guzmán, and Somohano-Rodríguez (2022); Lin et al. (2022)
	Company age	fage	Age of the company	SABI	García-Sánchez, Aibar-Guzmán, Aibar-Guzmán, and Somohano-Rodríguez (2022)
	ROA	ROA	Economic profitability	SABI	García-Sánchez, Aibar-Guzmán, Aibar-Guzmán, and Somohano-Rodríguez (2022); Lin et al. (2022)
COVID-19	(COVID)	1 = period 2020–2021 0 = the rest of the years	SABI		

Hummel & Szekely, 2022) to avoid biased results the model includes a set of control variables representing other CEO features, corporate governance mechanisms, and firm characteristics. These variables have been found to explain a company's sustainability reporting, in general, and SDG reporting, in particular. As regards the first group, gender is a dummy variable that takes the value of 1 if the CEO is a woman and 0 otherwise, and age represents the CEO's age. As regards corporate governance mechanisms, board size (bsize) represents the number of directors on the board; board independence (bindep) represents the percentage of independent directors on the board; board diversity (bdiversity) represents the percentage of female directors on the board; CEO duality is a dummy variable that takes the value of 1 if the CEO is also the chairperson of the board, and 0 otherwise; and CSR committee (CSRcom) is a dummy variable that assumes the value of 1 if there is a CSR commission on the board, and 0 otherwise. As for firm characteristics, firm size (fsize) is measured by the logarithm of total assets; company age (fage) measures the age of the company as the time elapsed since its creation. ROA reflects the economic profitability. Finally, we consider the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic (COVID), through a dummy variable that takes the value 1 for that period (2020 and 2021), and the value of 0 for the rest of the years. The data to measure these variables were obtained from the Iberian Balance Analysis System (SABI) database.

Table 3 summarizes the variables included in the model.

4 | RESULTS

4.1 | Descriptive statistics

Table 4 shows the descriptive statistics for the variables included in the model; the descriptive statistics for the numerical variables and the relative frequency of the dichotomous variables. Regarding the dependent variable (SDG), as can be seen in Panel A, it should be noted that the average score on the level of disclosure of information on the SDGs is quite low (3.069). Specifically, we can observe that a large part of the sample has a value of 0 and that one of the most obtained scores is 7 points in SDG. As regards the variables related to the CEO's professional and personal characteristics (Panel B and C), the average age of the CEOs of the IBEX-35 companies is 56 years, they have been occupying the position of CEO in their companies for an average of 7.36 years, and they are mostly men. Moreover, the average of the education level is 2.88, which means that the average education level of the CEOs of the IBEX-35 companies is higher than a bachelor's degree. The vast majority of the sample companies are headed by Spanish CEOs, specifically the 90.20%. It should be noted that our variable regarding CEO narcissism has a mean value of 3.0938, which, to some extent, confirms Kim et al.'s (2018) statement that almost all CEOs of leading companies tend to be narcissistic.

Table 5 shows the Pearson correlation coefficients. As can be seen, the coefficients and their significance demonstrate that there are no multicollinearity problems between the variables considered in the empirical analysis.

TABLE 4 Descriptive statistics

Panel A. dependent variable		
SDG score	Frequency relative	
Value 0	44.49%	
Value 1	4.90%	
Value 2	1.22%	
Value 3	5.71%	
Value 4	6.94%	
Value 5	6.12%	
Value 6	9.39%	
Value 7	10.20%	
Value 8	3.67%	
Value 9	6.53%	
Value 10	0.82%	
Value 11	0%	
SDG	Mean	Standard deviation
	3.0693	3.2729
Panel B. Independent and control variables (dummies)		
Variable	Frequency relative	
Nationality	90.20%	
Gender	96.73%	
CEO duality	23.27%	
CSR com	33.06%	
COVID	28.57%	
Panel C. Independent and control variables (numerical)		
Variable	Mean	Standard deviation
Education	2.8897	0.6529
Tenure	7.3673	6.9385
Narcissism	3.0938	1.5348
Age	56.2938	7.3732
bsize	12.6	2.7556
bindep	0.4972	0.1301
Diversity	0.2603	0.4151
fsize	9.9067	0.9347
fage	49.0204	40.1653
ROA	2.7206	8.4903
Industry	3.9714	2.5852
Year	4.0000	2.0040

In Table 6 we tested the correlation among the variables. Following the rule stated by Brooks (2008), the correlation coefficients do not indicate any collinearity problem, as the absolute values are less than 0.8 in all cases. Additionally, in order to verify that there is no collinearity among the variables of the model a Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) test was carried out which indicates that there is no evidence of multicollinearity, as the Centered Variance Inflation Factor is less than 10 in all cases.

TABLE 5 Pearson's correlations

	Sdg	Education	Nationality	Tenure	Narcissism	Gender	Age	Bsize	Bindep	Bdiversity	Ceoduality	Csrcom	Fsize	Fage	Roa	Covid	Industry	Year
sdg	1.0000																	
Education	0.1915	1.0000																
Nationality	0.1079	-0.0136	1.0000															
Tenure	0.0274	0.1664	0.1761	1.0000														
Narcissism	0.0909	-0.0019	0.0650	-0.0698	1.0000													
Gender	0.0664	0.0311	0.0605	-0.0097	0.1087	1.0000												
Age	0.0226	0.0366	0.0225	0.6048	-0.1100	0.0426	1.0000											
bsize	0.2303	-0.0223	0.0819	-0.2591	0.0002	-0.1236	-0.1348	1.0000										
bindep	0.1233	0.1033	-0.0973	0.0583	0.0221	0.0563	0.0740	-0.0113	1.0000									
bdiversity	0.1422	-0.0609	-0.0048	0.1593	0.0435	0.0223	0.0026	0.0781	0.1763	1.0000								
ceoduality	0.0356	0.0338	-0.1110	0.4688	0.0356	-0.0468	0.1736	-0.0955	0.0356	0.1151	1.0000							
csrcom	0.2534	0.0656	0.0273	0.1845	-0.0544	-0.0315	0.0568	0.0675	0.1691	0.1872	0.1675	1.0000						
fsize	0.2903	0.1043	0.0068	-0.3088	-0.0429	0.1862	-0.1164	0.4958	0.1987	0.1092	-0.1645	0.0734	1.0000					
fage	0.1048	-0.0185	0.1875	0.1026	0.1126	0.0119	0.2927	0.2604	-0.0736	0.1016	-0.0241	0.2146	0.3928	1.0000				
roa	0.0964	0.1079	0.1146	-0.0809	0.0936	-0.0589	-0.1852	-0.1313	0.0068	-0.0327	-0.0809	-0.0473	0.0067	0.0172	1.0000			
Covid	0.3406	-0.0456	-0.0651	0.0656	-0.0565	0.0363	0.0951	0.0723	0.1076	0.1971	-0.0275	0.4198	0.0816	0.0391	-0.1176	1.0000		
Industry	0.0564	-0.0116	0.1986	-0.1721	0.2021	0.2068	-0.1486	0.1687	0.1465	-0.0283	-0.2747	-0.2276	0.3025	-0.1300	-0.1007	0.0000	1.0000	
Year	0.4711	-0.0251	-0.0961	0.0875	-0.0413	0.0344	0.1262	0.0660	0.1145	0.2108	-0.0628	0.3818	0.1007	0.0491	-0.0769	0.7906	0.0000	1.0000

4.2 | Main results

Table 7 shows the results obtained in the estimating Equation (1) by using Tobit estimations for panel data. The results show that the CEO's level of education has a positive and statistically significant impact (coeff = 0.8392; $p < .01$) on the level of SDG disclosure made by the companies in the sample. Therefore, it can be said that those

TABLE 6 Correlation test

	Coefficient variance	Uncentered VIF	Centered VIF
Education	0.0768	23.7169	1.1475
Nationality	0.4278	13.5794	1.3302
Tenure	0.0016	6.1106	2.8660
Narcissism	0.0149	6.2747	1.2352
Gender	1.0630	1.2212	1.1814
Age	0.0010	124.6778	2.0943
bsize	0.0059	34.7227	1.5787
bindep	2.0851	19.3729	1.2366
bdiversity	0.1964	1.6547	1.1864
CEOduality	0.2526	2.0680	1.5869
CSRcom	0.1965	2.2865	1.5305
fsize	0.0785	273.5042	2.4037
fage	3.4200	4.8290	1.9349
ROA	0.0004	1.3077	1.1855
COVID	0.3960	3.9815	2.8439
Industry	0.0071	5.6614	1.6802
Year	0.0201	2.881845	2.8306

TABLE 7 Main results

	SDG coefficient (Std. err)	SDG2	SDG3
Education	0.8392*** (0.2667)	0.2702*** (0.0837)	0.0880** (0.0402)
Nationality	1.9179*** (0.6089)	0.5927*** (0.1977)	0.2276** (0.0950)
Tenure	-0.0277 (0.0396)	-0.0108 (0.0124)	-0.0063 (0.0059)
Narcissism	0.2531** (0.1177)	0.0605 (0.0369)	0.0078 (0.0177)
Gender	0.3811 (0.9924)	0.1645 (0.3116)	0.1351 (0.1498)
Age	0.0308 (0.0319)	0.0068 (0.0100)	0.0028 (0.0048)
bsize	0.1647** (0.0741)	0.0423 (0.0232)	0.0179 (0.0111)
bindep	0.1382 (1.3899)	-0.1591 (0.4364)	0.0194 (0.2098)
bdiversity	0.1298 (0.4266)	0.0312 (0.1339)	0.0397 (0.0644)
CEOduality	0.9476 (0.4838)	0.3578** (0.1519)	0.1795** (0.0730)
CSRcom	0.3861 (0.4267)	0.1038 (0.1340)	0.0396 (0.0644)
fsize	0.7805*** (0.2697)	0.2328*** (0.0846)	0.1078*** (0.0407)
fage	-0.0096* (0.0056)	-0.0025 (0.0017)	-0.0006 (0.0008)
ROA	0.0436** (0.0208)	0.0173*** (0.0065)	0.0051 (0.0031)
COVID	-0.6413 (0.6057)	-0.1427 (0.1902)	-0.0063 (0.0914)
Industry	-0.0673 (0.0815)	-0.0205 (0.0256)	-0.0173 (0.0123)
Year	0.8623*** (0.1365)	0.2528*** (0.0428)	0.0919*** (0.0206)

*** $p < .01$; ** $p < .05$; * $p < .1$.

IBEX-35 companies whose CEOs have a higher level of education tend to disclose a higher level of information related to the SDGs. This result confirms the Hypothesis H1, that states that educational background determines how CEOs perceive the business role in achieving the SDGs and favors their awareness regarding their firms' disclosure needs.

Moreover, the results show that the CEO's nationality has a positive and statistically significant impact (coeff = 1.9179; $p < .01$) on the level of SDG disclosure made by her/his company. Taking into account that this variable is a dummy coded as 0 (foreign CEOs) and 1 (Spanish CEOs), this finding indicates that those IBEX-35 firms with Spanish CEOs tend to disclose a higher level of information on the SDGs and, therefore, the Hypothesis H2 can be accepted. Thus, our findings indicate that, as posited, the fact of working in a company located in their own country makes CEOs more inclined to disclose information on the SDGs (Hernández et al., 2010).

The results also show that narcissism has a positive and statistically significant impact (coef = 0.2531; $p < .05$) on the level of SDG disclosure made by companies, which allows us to confirm the argument that business commitment to the 2030 Agenda provides narcissistic CEOs with an opportunity to attract attention and enhance their public image and reputation, thereby satisfying their psychological needs of admiration and praise (Al-Shanmari et al. 2019). Thus, those IBEX-35 companies with more narcissistic CEO disclose more information about the SDGs, which supports Hypothesis H4.

As for CEO tenure, no significant relationship was found between this variable and SDG disclosure. In the scope of our sample, CEO tenure does not affect the disclosure level of information

TABLE 8 Complementary results

	Equation 2	Equation 3	Equation 4	Equation 5
Education	4.4130* (2.2472)	0.4948 (1.0172)	1.3100*** (0.2939)	0.9866*** (0.2870)
Nationality	-4.9935 (4.5256)	-0.3692 (2.5996)	1.8819** (0.7792)	0.3153 (1.3064)
Tenure	0.6560*** (0.1893)	0.1932* (0.1120)	-0.2216 (0.1511)	-0.0346 (0.0407)
Narcissism	-2.2357** (0.9000)	-0.0757 (0.6005)	-0.3241* (0.1670)	-0.2762 (0.3995)
Age*gender	0.0055 (0.2715)	-		
Age*education	-0.0560 (0.0384)	-		
Age*nationality	0.1242 (0.0812)	-		
Age*tenure	-0.0108*** (0.0031)	-		
Age*narcissism	0.0417*** (0.0159)	-		
Education*nationality		0.8914 (0.8663)		
Education*tenure		-0.0706** (0.0351)		
Education*narc		0.0994 (0.2075)		
Tenure*gender			0.0328 (0.2787)	
Tenure*nationality			-0.0400 (0.1384)	
Tenure*narcissism			0.0833*** (0.1738)	
Narcissism *gender				-0.1716 (1.0928)
Narcissim*nationality				0.5878 (0.4211)
Gender	-0.3200 (15.7337)	0.2687 (.9825)	-0.2777 (2.1362)	-1.0797 (4.4358)
Age	0.0602 (0.1202)	0.0345 (0.0333)	0.0539 (0.0329)	0.0284 (0.0318)
bsize	0.1964*** (0.0709)	0.1815** (0.0738)	0.1371* (0.7129)	0.1671** (0.0738)
bindep	0.6829 (1.3821)	0.2842 (1.3833)	-0.3023 (1.3326)	0.0261 (1.3877)
bdiversity	0.0770 (0.3980)	0.0230 (0.4279)	0.0006 (0.4088)	0.1699 (0.4258)
CEOduality	1.6386*** (0.4865)	0.9972** (0.4838)	1.1646** (0.4869)	0.8678* (0.4979)
CSRcom	0.3872 (0.4251)	0.0728 (0.4557)	0.2360 (0.4495)	0.1902 (0.4475)
fsize	0.6940*** (0.2558)	0.6905** (0.2699)	0.6701** (0.2628)	0.7145** (0.2784)
fage	-0.0143*** (0.0054)	-0.0094* (0.0056)	-0.0126** (0.0055)	-0.0034 (0.0057)
ROA	0.0264 (0.0204)	0.0358* (0.0218)	0.0122 (0.0212)	0.0395* (0.0209)
COVID	-0.7741 (0.5681)	-0.6087 (0.6005)	-0.8477 (0.5858)	-0.5539 (0.6070)
Industry	-0.0212 (0.0768)	-0.0406 (0.0824)	-0.0409 (0.0790)	-0.0891 (0.0830)
Year	0.8448*** (0.1281)	0.8807*** (0.1353)	0.9104*** (0.1312)	0.8715*** (0.1365)

on the SDGs. Therefore, the related hypothesis (H3) cannot be accepted.

Regarding control variables, the results show a positive and significant relationship between the level of SDG disclosure and the following variables: board size (coeff = 0.1647: $p < .05$), firm size (coeff = 0.7805: $p < .01$), and ROA (coeff = 0.0436: $p < .05$). In addition, a significant and negative relationship was observed for firm age (coeff = -0.0096, $p < .1$). As for the remaining variables, no significant effect on the dependent variable was observed.

To check the robustness of the results, we have performed a recoding on the dependent variables (second and third columns in Table 7), observing that with the variations made in the dependent variable, the results continue to reflect the same patterns, indicating a high level of robustness of the results obtained by the model, with the exception of narcissism, which was not statistically significant.

5 | COMPLEMENTARY ANALYSIS

Considering that (1) it is possible that, individually considered, some CEO characteristics do not have a significant impact on the level of SDG disclosure but may have a significant impact in combination with other CEO attributes (Chu et al., 2022; Villalba-Ríos et al., 2022), and (2) some of the CEO attributes analyzed in our study can reinforce or inhibit the effect of the remaining ones on SDG disclosure (Khan et al., 2020; Villalba-Ríos et al., 2022), we conduct a complementary analysis with the aim of looking for the profile of the CEOs that are more likely to foster SDG reporting by their companies. Thus, following Villalba-Ríos et al. (2022, pp. 356–357), we look for a CEO profile as “a set of attributes rather than a single characteristic that reflects a CEO’s cognitive framework and behavioral preferences” as regards sustainability reporting. Therefore, we developed a regression model for each independent variable,

including its interaction with the remaining CEO attributes, as well as the same control variables included in Equation (1). These regression models are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{SDG}_{i,t} = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{education}_{i,t} + \beta_2 \text{nationality}_{i,t} + \beta_3 \text{tenure}_{i,t} \\ & + \beta_4 \text{narcissism}_{i,t} + \beta_5 \text{age} * \text{gender}_{i,t} + \beta_6 \text{age} * \text{education}_{i,t} \\ & + \beta_7 \text{age} * \text{nationality}_{i,t} + \beta_8 \text{age} * \text{tenure}_{i,t} \\ & + \beta_9 \text{age} * \text{narcissism}_{i,t} + \beta_{10} \text{gender}_{i,t} + \beta_{11} \text{age}_{i,t} + \beta_{12} \text{bsize}_{i,t} \\ & + \beta_{13} \text{bindep}_{i,t} + \beta_{14} \text{bdiversity}_{i,t} + \beta_{15} \text{CEOduality}_{i,t} \\ & + \beta_{16} \text{CSRcom}_{i,t} + \beta_{17} \text{fsize}_{i,t} + \beta_{18} \text{fage}_{i,t} + \beta_{19} \text{ROA}_{i,t} \\ & + \beta_{20} \text{COVID}_{i,t} + \beta_{21} \text{Industry}_i + \beta_{22} \text{Year}_t + \varepsilon_{i,t} + \eta_{i,t} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{SDG}_{i,t} = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{education}_{i,t} + \beta_2 \text{nationality}_{i,t} + \beta_3 \text{tenure}_{i,t} \\ & + \beta_4 \text{narcissism}_{i,t} + \beta_5 \text{education} * \text{gender}_{i,t} \\ & + \beta_6 \text{education} * \text{nationality}_{i,t} + \beta_7 \text{education} * \text{tenure}_{i,t} \\ & + \beta_8 \text{education} * \text{narcissism}_{i,t} + \beta_9 \text{gender}_{i,t} \\ & + \beta_{10} \text{age}_{i,t} + \beta_{11} \text{bsize}_{i,t} + \beta_{12} \text{bindep}_{i,t} + \beta_{13} \text{bdiversity}_{i,t} \\ & + \beta_{14} \text{CEOduality}_{i,t} + \beta_{15} \text{CSRcom}_{i,t} + \beta_{16} \text{fsize}_{i,t} + \beta_{17} \text{fage}_{i,t} \\ & + \beta_{18} \text{ROA}_{i,t} + \beta_{19} \text{COVID}_{i,t} + \beta_{20} \text{Industry}_i + \beta_{21} \text{Year}_t + \varepsilon_{i,t} \\ & + \eta_{i,t} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{SDG}_{i,t} = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{education}_{i,t} + \beta_2 \text{nationality}_{i,t} + \beta_3 \text{tenure}_{i,t} \\ & + \beta_4 \text{narcissism}_{i,t} + \beta_5 \text{tenure} * \text{gender}_{i,t} \\ & + \beta_6 \text{tenure} * \text{nationality}_{i,t} + \beta_7 \text{tenure} * \text{narcissism}_{i,t} \\ & + \beta_8 \text{gender}_{i,t} + \beta_9 \text{age}_{i,t} + \beta_{10} \text{bsize}_{i,t} + \beta_{11} \text{bindep}_{i,t} \\ & + \beta_{12} \text{bdiversity}_{i,t} + \beta_{13} \text{CEOduality}_{i,t} + \beta_{14} \text{CSRcom}_{i,t} \\ & + \beta_{15} \text{fsize}_{i,t} + \beta_{16} \text{fage}_{i,t} + \beta_{17} \text{ROA}_{i,t} + \beta_{18} \text{COVID}_{i,t} \\ & + \beta_{19} \text{Industry}_i + \beta_{20} \text{Year}_t + \varepsilon_{i,t} + \eta_{i,t} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{SDG}_{i,t} = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{education}_{i,t} + \beta_2 \text{nationality}_{i,t} + \beta_3 \text{tenure}_{i,t} \\ & + \beta_4 \text{narcissism}_{i,t} + \beta_5 \text{narcissism} * \text{gender}_{i,t} \\ & + \beta_6 \text{narcissism} * \text{nationality}_{i,t} + \beta_7 \text{gender}_{i,t} \\ & + \beta_8 \text{age}_{i,t} + \beta_9 \text{bsize}_{i,t} + \beta_{10} \text{bindep}_{i,t} + \beta_{11} \text{bdiversity}_{i,t} \\ & + \beta_{12} \text{CEOduality}_{i,t} + \beta_{13} \text{CSRcom}_{i,t} + \beta_{14} \text{fsize}_{i,t} + \beta_{15} \text{fage}_{i,t} \\ & + \beta_{16} \text{ROA}_{i,t} + \beta_{17} \text{COVID}_{i,t} + \beta_{18} \text{Industry}_i + \beta_{19} \text{Year}_t + \varepsilon_{i,t} \\ & + \eta_{i,t} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Thus, the above models test the moderating effect that one specific CEO attribute has on the remaining CEO attributes through the interaction between them; which will require that $\beta_i > 0$, indicating that the effect of this attribute is enhanced by the presence of the other (García-Sánchez et al., 2023).

Table 8 shows the findings obtained for each model. Regarding the individual effects of CEO attributes, as can be seen, the positive and significant impact of the CEO education level on SDG reporting observed in the main analysis is maintained in the new models, except in model 3, where it has no significant effect. However, the

positive and statistically significant effect of nationality is only maintained in the model represented by Equation (4); while, and in contrast to the main analysis, in the case of CEO narcissism, its effect on SDG disclosure is negative, indicating that companies with less narcissistic CEOs disclose more information on the SDGs. Therefore, and in line with the robustness analysis performed, we cannot conclude that narcissism has a clearly positive effect on SDG disclosure.

As regards the joint effect of CEO attributes on SDG disclosure, we observe a significant effect for some combinations. First, in the second model (Equation (2)) the combined variable of age and tenure has a significant and negative effect (coeff = -0.1080 ; $p < .01$), which means that the initial positive effect of CEO tenure on SDG reporting is being moderated negatively by CEOs age. Therefore, CEOs shorter tenure disclose more information on the SDGs, and this relationship is pronounced the older the CEO is. In summary, we can say that the shorter the CEO's tenure and the older the CEO's age, the more information they disclose about the SDGs. To some extent, this result contradicts the finding obtained by Khan et al. (2020), who found that the negative effect of CEO tenure on CSR was greater in the case of CEOs who have longer expected period of service (i.e., younger CEOs) than when they are close to retirement (i.e., older CEOs). However, the combination of age and narcissism has a significant and positive effect (coeff = 0.04170 ; $p < .01$), which means that companies with older and narcissistic CEOs disclose more SDG information, which means that the initial negative effect of CEO narcissism on SDG reporting is corrected by longer age. Thus, those companies led by narcissist CEOs who are older disclose more information on the SDGs. In this case, it appears that CEO age counterbalances the initial negative effect of narcissism on SDG reporting. In our opinion, this could be since being older makes CEOs with a narcissistic personality enhance this attribute, positively affecting SDG reporting.

Second, in the third model (Equation (3)) it can be observed a significant and negative effect for the combination of education and tenure (coeff = -0.0706 ; $p < .05$), which means that the initial positive effect of CEO tenure on SDG reporting is being moderated negatively by CEOs educational level. Therefore, CEOs with shorter tenure disclose more information on the SDGs, and this relationship is pronounced the older the CEO is. In summary, we can say that the shorter the CEO's tenure and the higher their educational level, the more information they disclose about the SDGs. Finally, in the fourth model (Equation (4)) a significant and positive effect of the combination of tenure and narcissism (coeff = 0.0833 ; $p < .01$), which means that the initial negative effect of CEO narcissism on SDG reporting is corrected by longer tenure. Thus, those companies led by narcissist CEOs who have also been in the company longer disclose more information on the SDGs. In this case, it appears that CEO tenure counterbalances the initial negative effect of narcissism on SDG reporting. In our opinion, this could be due to the fact that having been in the company longer makes CEOs with a narcissistic personality enhance this attribute as they feel more secure in their position.

6 | DISCUSSION AND IMPLICATIONS

6.1 | Summary of findings

Firstly, we found that the average score on the level of disclosure of information on the SDGs by Spanish leading companies is quite low (3.069). This value is lower than the mean value obtained by Hummel and Szekely (2022) for European companies (4.18). However, our result is in line with that obtained by García-Sánchez, Aibar-Guzmán, Aibar-Guzmán, and Somohano-Rodríguez (2022), who found that only 3.24% of the leading firms worldwide have integrated the SDG into their information systems.

Secondly, we found that some CEO attributes, namely education level, nationality, and narcissism, positively affect the level of disclosure of SDG information, while CEO tenure has no significant impact on SDG reporting. As regards education level, we found that those IBEX-35 companies whose CEOs have a higher level of education tend to disclose a higher level of information related to the SDGs. Our finding is in line with most prior studies documenting a positive association between the CEO educational background and CSR reporting (Huang, 2013; Lewis et al., 2014; Ma et al., 2019; Malik et al., 2020) as well as the findings obtained by García-Sánchez, Aibar-Guzmán, Aibar-Guzmán, and Somohano-Rodríguez (2022) regarding SDG reporting.

Regarding CEOs nationality, our results indicate that those IBEX-35 firms with Spanish CEOs tend to disclose a higher level of SDG information. As noted above, this finding suggests that working in a company located in their own country makes CEOs more inclined to disclose information about the SDGs (Hernández et al., 2010). Again, this result confirms those obtained by Al-Duais et al. (2021) and Ren et al. (2021). However, in interpreting this finding, it should be borne in mind that most of the CEOs of the companies in the sample are Spanish.

With regard to CEO narcissism, we found that those IBEX-35 companies with more narcissistic CEO disclose more information about the SDGs. In this sense, our findings challenge the assumption that those traits, such as narcissism, that are commonly considered as the “dark side” of an individual's personality are detrimental to society (Al-Shammari et al., 2019) by showing that narcissism may also have a “bright side”. Furthermore, this finding is consistent with the results obtained by Petrenko et al. (2016) and Al-Shammari et al. (2019). However, this result should be interpreted carefully as it has not been confirmed by the robustness analysis.

Finally, although we expected CEO tenure to negatively affect SDG reporting, our findings indicate that this variable does not affect the level of SDG disclosure. This finding is consistent with that obtained by Al-Shammari et al. (2019), who also found no significant relationship between CEO tenure and SDG reporting. However, when analyzing the joint effect of CEO attributes on SDG disclosure, we found a significant effect for some combinations. Thus, the combination of long tenure and narcissism has a positive significant effect on SDG reporting, which suggests that to the extent that narcissistic CEOs seek attention and enhance their public image and reputation, CEO narcissism may counteract the expected negative effect of tenure on SDG disclosure.

6.2 | Research implications

This research contributes to literature in several ways. Firstly, it adds a new type of determinant of SDG reporting (the CEO's characteristics) to those identified in previous studies (García-Sánchez, Aibar-Guzmán, Aibar-Guzmán, & Somohano-Rodríguez, 2022; Pizzi et al., 2021; Rosati & Faria, 2019a, 2019b; van der Waal & Thijssens, 2020) and provides a new conceptual lens for analyzing the drivers of SDG disclosure. Previous studies have focused on institutional-level factors firm-level, and governance-level factors that may affect a firm's propensity to disclose SDG information. However, apart from García-Sánchez, Aibar-Guzmán, Aibar-Guzmán, and Somohano-Rodríguez (2022), who analyzed the effect of two CEO personal attributes (gender and educational background), to the authors' knowledge no previous study has analyzed the influence of CEO demographic characteristics, values, and cognitive styles on SDG reporting. Thus, this study extends the empirical evidence on the determinants of SDG reporting by considering a broad set of observable and unobservable characteristics of a company's CEO, including both personal (education level and nationality) and professional (tenure) attributes as well personality traits (narcissism), which have not been previously analyzed in the context of the 2030 Agenda. By showing “why and how” the attributes of the CEO affect a company's level of SDG disclosure, our study extends the current understanding of the implications of CEO characteristics on corporate decisions. Specifically, by demonstrating that CEO narcissism has a positive impact on corporate transparency in relation to the SDGs, we show that this CEO personality trait may have a “bright side” with regard corporate sustainability. Furthermore, our findings underline the importance of the CEO's education level.

Secondly, in addition to identifying the individual CEO attributes that independently affect SDG reporting, we also analyze the effect of the interaction among the different CEO attributes on SDG reporting. In this sense, we add novel evidence to the limited research of how several CEO attributes jointly affect CSR initiatives (Chu et al., 2022; Villalba-Ríos et al., 2022). We show that some CEO attributes, when combined with others, can produce stronger or contradictory effects on SDG reporting and thus answer the question posed by Villalba-Ríos et al. (2022) by providing empirical evidence that CEO profile matters for CSR activities. Our results indicate that CEOs with certain profiles promote SDG reporting. Specifically, we show that companies with older and narcissist CEOs as well as companies with narcissist CEOs who have been in the company longer disclose more information on the SDGs. Moreover, conversely, other CEO profiles appear to hinder SDG reporting. In this regard, our findings suggest that companies with younger CEOs and who have been in the company longer and also companies with less educated and longer-serving CEOs disclose less information on the SDGs.

Finally, this research informs the UET by extending the study of the individual and joint effect of various CEO characteristics to the context of the 2030 Agenda. First, our results confirm the central tenets of the UET by demonstrating that CEO's personal traits, values, and experiences influence their decisions about SDG reporting. Specifically, we show that CEO's education level and nationality shape

the way they interpret the context by favoring their orientation towards sustainability, and that a narcissistic personality has a similar effect. Second, we extend the scope of the UET by suggesting that not only the CEO's individual attributes mold her/his "personal construal" of strategic choices but also the various combinations of these attributes have different effects on CEO decision-making. We show that the way different characteristics of CEOs combine in a specific profile influences their decisions. Thus, we advance the study of the CEO's profile to explain the decisions made by the CEO (Villalba-Ríos et al., 2022). In this sense, our findings indicate that SDG reporting is promoted/hindered by certain CEO profiles.

6.3 | Practical implications

In terms of the practical implications of this research, it highlights the importance of "choosing the CEO well" (Weng & Chen, 2017, p. 224) to overcome the challenging task of achieving the 2030 Agenda. In this regard, our results can help companies interested in fostering commitment to the 2030 Agenda when selecting their CEOs. In particular, our findings indicate that, if a firm seeks to improve its reporting behavior with respect to its contribution to the SDGs, its executive hiring policies should value the educational level, local ties, and narcissism of candidates. Indeed, our findings suggest that SDG reporting can be promoted by CEOs with certain profiles, providing a picture of the kind of business leaders who can help society move towards achieving of the 2030 Agenda.

Moreover, our findings could orientate firms interested in sustainability reporting when designing incentive systems (e.g., tenure-related incentives). Finally, at the societal level, the results highlight the importance of education as a means of raising awareness of the need for sustainable development.

7 | CONCLUSIONS

The 2030 Agenda and the SDGs underline the importance of an active participation of companies in the achievement of sustainable development, appealing to their voluntary commitment to the common good and the sustainability of the planet. As the main responsible for a company's strategies and disclosure policies, including those related to CSR, the CEO can not only promote commitment to the SDGs and determine the SDGs most pertinent to their field of business, but also influence the disclosure of information about them.

This study adds to the growing stream of research in the upper echelons literature exploring the influence of CEO attributes on corporate sustainability and contributes to CSR literature by showing that individual CEO attributes should not be considered a priori as "good or bad" for corporate sustainability, as their interaction forming a certain profile may affect sustainable development-oriented decision-making in different ways, reinforcing or counteracting individual effects, and that there may be different profiles (various combinations of attributes) favoring or inhibiting such decision-making.

Despite its interest and practical usefulness, this research is subject to some limitations related mainly to the sample. Its small size and the fact that it focuses on a single country (Spain) and on the largest companies may limit the generalizability of the results. Therefore, future research could adopt a broader scope expanding the sample to companies from more countries and considering SMEs. On the other hand, due to problems related to data availability, we have focused on certain variables and measurements of these variables. Future studies may expand the set of CEO attributes to be analyzed and employ alternative measures of SDG disclosure and CEO attributes. Thus, we have considered education level, but not the type of education, which several studies have shown to influence the way individuals process information. Therefore, future studies could extend this research by considering the type of education received both in terms of bachelor's, master's and doctoral degrees. Similarly, when analyzing CEO nationality, we distinguish between local and foreign CEOs with respect to Spain. In this sense, it would be interesting to broaden the discussion taking into account the origin of foreign CEOs. For example, future studies could consider the case of foreign CEOs whose country of origin is one in which the company has subsidiaries. It would also be interesting to analyze how would affect the functional roles of the CEO's career tracks their disclosure choices of SDG information. As regards CEO narcissism, we used the photos of the CEO published in the annual reports because we found this measure very revealing and intuitive. However, we are aware that there are other alternative measures of narcissism (e.g., signature size, the level of the CEO's presence in press releases), use of which is likely to produce more robust results. These alternative measures could be used in future studies.

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